

ORGANIZING NEW TOURISM DESTINATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. At present, the development of theoretical, methodological and practical approaches to solve the problems of sustainable development of national tourism in our republic, the formation of the market of tourist products, the economic methods of regulating the activities of this sector and the organizational structures of its management, and the improvement of the economic mechanism of tourism development are of great importance.

Keywords: Tourism industry, international tourism, transport services, foreign investments, modern marketing, tourist firm, business, marketing concept, transport service.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, fundamental reforms are being carried out in all sectors of the economy. In particular, the State attaches great importance to the development of tourism. The main infrastructures that make up the tourism sector: means of accommodation, catering service and transport service. Based on this, transport services play a key role in the development of the tourism sector. The development and improvement of transport services creates convenience for tourists and eases their travel. Through this, it is possible to achieve the development of tourism in the country.

International tourism is the growing need of people to get to know countries, have fun, have fun, spend their free time productively, restore their health, participate in world and sports competitions, enrich their spiritual world, the traditions of other nations. It occupies a special place in the quest to know the habit and lifestyle.

It should be noted that, if we look into the past, humanity has always changed its sphere of action in space, discovered new lands, enriched its lifestyle, and strived for the further development and improvement of social relations. This has a positive effect on the formation and development of a person, and tourism, especially its international direction, is of decisive importance. International tourism is very multifaceted, and its components are hotel, catering, transport, trade, recreation and sightseeing, and many other areas and processes are interconnected and act.

The role and importance of international tourism in the world economy is increasing year by year, and it is becoming one of the most profitable sectors in the world.

In the development of the tourism sector, it is also necessary to take into account the fact that many people who lived in our republic before or who belong to the Uzbek nationality live outside our country. They have a strong desire to come to our republic and visit the land where their ancestors lived. In this regard, there are real conditions for the development of tourism in our republic. This is an incomplete list of factors that have a positive effect on the successful development of tourism in Uzbekistan, the level of their use is quite low. Only 5-8 percent of the more than 8,000 cultural and natural heritage sites in our republic are used for tourist purposes.

In order to further develop and improve the field of tourism in our country, in the future, actively attracting foreign investments, world brands, creating favorable conditions for business in the field of tourism, modern objects of tourism infrastructure, first of all, hotels, transport-logistics, are being built in all regions of our republic. It is important to build structures, engineering and communication facilities, and in this process it is important to take into account that the new facilities fully meet the international standards and the demands and needs of tourists.

In our republic, a wide range of measures are being implemented in order to ensure the economic stability of families. In particular, favorable conditions are being created for the establishment and development of family business and private entrepreneurship, handicrafts. In particular, the fact that many benefits are being introduced in this field helps to bring out the entrepreneurial talent of families.

In the organization of tourism services, first of all, comprehensive measures are implemented to ensure the safety of the life and health of tourists and excursionists in places where tourists are accommodated, in food outlets, when moving around the territory of the republic, when organizing visits to tourism facilities. Increasing tourism in the country can be developed rapidly. More complete and effective use of the existing huge tourism potential, along with traditional cultural and historical tourism, other potential types of tourism - pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, treatment-health, rural, industrial, the rapid development of business tourism and other types, the strengthening of the social importance of tourism due to the development of children, teenagers and youth tourism, family tourism, social tourism for the elderly, the establishment of new tourism destinations in the regions, their passporting, tourism destinations and tourism development and implementation of national and regional programs for the comprehensive development of domestic, inbound and outbound tourism, aimed at the formation of uniform national registers on objects, international cooperation in the field of tourism activities, first of all, the UN World Tourism Organization, foreign countries on tourism prestigious international and national organization horse tourism services have been determined through the decisions taken such as expanding cooperation with active participants of the regional and world markets, Uzbekistan's participation in universal international conventions and agreements regulating the field of tourism, introducing international and interstate standards and norms into the practice of tourism activities.

It is imperative that all employees in the business know and understand marketing research. Because, for the purpose of long-term activity, it is possible to fully realize the business only by knowing the field of marketing.

Nowadays, every tourist enterprise takes financial responsibility for every operation that caused damage. For this reason, a tourist company should always be prepared for the risks of business activity. This level of risk reduction can be achieved by using the marketing concept correctly and accurately. Of course, the essence of marketing is not only competition in the market. An even more important goal for a travel company is the development and sale of tour products, an increase in income and profit, and an increase in profitability. Modern marketing is related to every activity and functional structure of tourism companies, and the sales methods of marketing are the daily work of the processes of travel company teams.

Directed and comprehensive investment policy should become the main source of creation and financing of the tourism industry. At the initial stages of the transition to market

relations in the field of tourism, the traditional state system of attracting investment in tourism can be used as an important tool for managing the processes taking place in this field.

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